

Real-time surgical simulation by Proper Generalized Decomposition techniques

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Abstract. The real-time computer-based simulation of surgery has proven to be an appealing alternative to traditional surgical simulators. Amongst other advantages, computer-based simulators provide considerable savings on time and maintenance costs, and allow trainees to practice their surgical skills in a safe environment as often as necessary. However, in spite of the current computer capabilities, computational surgery continues to be a challenging field of research. One of its major issues is the high speed at which complex problems in continuum mechanics have to be solved so that haptic interfaces can render a realistic sense of touch (generally, feedback rates of 500–1 000 Hz are required).

The work here presented introduces some novel numerical methods for the interactive simulation of two usual surgical procedures: cutting and tearing of soft tissues. The common framework of these two methods is the use of the Proper Generalized Decomposition (PGD) for the generation of computational vademecums (Chinesta et al. 2013), i. e. general meta-solutions of parametric high-dimensional problems that can be evaluated at feedback rates compatible with haptic environments.

In the case of cutting, computational vademecums are used jointly with XFEM-based techniques, and the computing workload is distributed into an off-line and an on-line stage. During the off-line stage, both a computational vademecum for any position of a load and the displacements produced by a set of cuts are pre-computed for the organ under consideration. Thus, during the on-line stage, the pre-computed results are properly combined together to obtain in real-time the response to the actions driven by the user (Quesada et al. 2016). Concerning tearing, a computational vademecum is obtained from a parametric equation based on continuum damage mechanics. The complexity of the model is reduced by Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) techniques, and the vademecum is incorporated into an explicit incremental formulation that can be viewed as a sort of time integrator.

By way of example, the cutting method is applied to the simulation of a corneal refractive surgical procedure known as radial keratotomy (Fig. 1), whereas the tearing method focuses on the simulation of laparoscopic cholecystectomy (i. e. the removal of the gallbladder) (Fig. 2). In both cases, the implemented methods show excellent performances in terms of feedback rates, and produce very realistic simulations from the visual and haptic point of view.

Keywords: Proper Generalized Decomposition; computational vademecums; computational surgery; surgical simulation; real-time computing; cutting of soft tissues; tearing of soft tissues; XFEM; POD; continuum damage mechanics

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Data-based parametric modeling of human liver anatomy for patient-specific real-time deformable models in computational surgery

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In this study a parametric Finite Element (FE) model of the human liver is built accounting for anatomical variability from patient to patient. An explicit parametric solution is computed at once for the whole “family” of anatomical shapes with prescribed loads and material properties using Proper Generalized Decomposition (PGD), allowing real-time computation.

The shapes of human livers were reconstructed from 712 Magnetic Resonance Images acquired at IRCAD (Institut de Recherche contre les Cancers de l'Appareil Digestif, Strasbourg). All the shapes were registered to a template liver. Non-rigid registration was performed using Iterative Closest Point with Thin Plate Spline parametrization. Several dimensionality reductions techniques were applied, in a comparative way, to find the intrinsic coordinates ζ_i describing a lower dimensional manifold of the liver geometries. These include Principal Component Analysis (PCA), kernel Principal Component Analysis (k-PCA), Locally Linear Embedding (LLE) and t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE). Finally, the livers biomechanical behavior was taken into account using a quasi-static hyper-elastic material model and PGD was used to compute numerical solutions for displacement fields \mathbf{u} under prescribed loads as an explicit function of the shape parameters ζ_i .

Based on the quality of segmentation, only 678 segmented liver shapes were retained for the study. The correspondence process gave good results to fit the majority of the livers. Since the database contains a large variety of anatomical shapes, we observed that linear dimensionality reduction techniques like PCA are unable to find low dimensional representations for the whole family of shapes. On the other hand, nonlinear techniques like (k-PCA, LLE, t-SNE) are more suitable to produce low dimensional mappings in terms of reduced shape parameters ζ_i . A nonlinear greedy algorithm is used to compute a reduced order representation.

The main advantage of generating an explicit solution $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\zeta}, p_2, \dots, p_D)$ (with \mathbf{x} the space coordinate, $\boldsymbol{\zeta}$ the shape-parameter coordinate and (p_2, \dots, p_D) additional coordinates that are introduced to parametrize loads and material properties), is that a fully customizable deformable organ model is readily available without the need to go through mesh generation, boundary conditions assignment and FE solution all over again for each patient. Since the solution is pre-computed offline, visualization of particular load-material-shape combination can be done practically in real time. The model can be thought of as a fully customizable virtual deformable twin of the patient's liver.

Keywords: human liver; statistical shape model; dimensionality reduction; model order reduction

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Source localization of uterine activity using Maximum Entropy on the Mean approach

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Abstract. This study evaluates the ability of distributed source localization method to accurately estimate the location of the sources of activity, as well as their sensitivity to the spatial extent of such sources when using EHG data. We used here realistic simulations of uterine electrical activity, taking into account the 16 electrodes for recording EHG signal, and involving a realistically shaped uterus model. A Data Driven Parcellization (DDP) method [1] was used to segment the uterus surface into non-overlapping regions. Our results showed that the localization were sensitive to spatial extents of the sources (ranging from 11 cm^2 to 29 cm^2), and also to the number and size of the regions defining the model. Our analysis of the evolution of the real sources during contraction showed a nonlinear propagation of uterine electrical activity.

Keywords: Maximum Entropy on the mean; Data Driven parcellization DDP; nonlinear propagation of uterine electrical activity

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Dynamic Viscoelastic Properties of a Fiber Composite Phantom for MRE

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Abstract:

Magnetic Resonance Elastography (MRE) is a non-invasive imaging technique employed to assess biological tissue properties (typically shear stiffness) by inducing the propagation of mechanical waves in the region of interest and measuring the tissue response by means of phase contrast magnetic resonance imaging [1]. The challenge in employing MRE on muscular tissue is to characterize a non-homogeneous, viscoelastic, and anisotropic material through an inverse approach able to identify regional variation of tissue viscoelastic properties from material response to harmonic mechanical loading.

Different inverse engineering techniques can be used to identify material properties either by direct local inversion of Navier's equations or by iterative methods aiming at minimizing the mismatch between the experimental results and simulation predictions. The inverse problem can be quite a formidable task for complex material behaviour involving anisotropy and viscoelasticity. The use of phantom composite materials with a-priori known mechanical properties which mimic the anisotropic frequency dependent response of skeletal muscle tissues can be a suitable strategy to set up identification methods.

In this work, we propose a finite element model able to predict the macroscopic response of the fiber-reinforced micro-composite used as a phantom material.

A regular cross-ply micro fiber layers immersed in an isotropic PVA gel matrix has been simulated by modeling a unit cell of the composite and considering the material response as that of an infinite repetition of the representative unit cell. Known viscoelastic properties in the frequency domain have been assumed for the constituents (fibers and matrix) and periodic boundary conditions have been used to replicate the behaviour of adjacent cells not included in the model.

The homogenized macroscopic constitutive model is then used to predict the response of the phantom subjected to harmonic loading. The effect of fiber density and the effect of macroscopic anisotropic material response is assessed in terms of displacement amplitude and phase angle in a frequency domain steady state dynamic finite element simulation of propagation of steady shear waves.

The model will be used in the future to design optimal mechanical properties of the phantom material to be employed in MRE experiments and set up of inverse identification approaches. This study aimed to develop a model to accurately predict the acceleration of structural systems during an earthquake. The acceleration and applied force of a structure were measured at current time step and the velocity and displacement were estimated through linear integration.

Keywords: Magnetic Resonance Elastography (MRE); Finite Element models; Steady State Dynamic

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Modelling the adaptation of skeletal muscles in response to isometric exercise

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Abstract. Exercise-induced skeletal muscle adaptation occurs over time through changes in mechanical and neural properties of the muscle targeted by exercise. In this study, a computational model describing the adaptation of skeletal muscles in response to isometric exercise is used to investigate the neural adaptation mechanisms.

A systematic review of the experimental studies on isometric exercise was performed. The review focused on randomized controlled studies involving healthy, normal-weight, young (aged between 18-30) subjects, and studies which included the measurement of the changes in maximal voluntary contraction (MVC) of the target muscle. These criteria yielded a total of 56 experimental studies. When grouped based on the specific exercise type and the muscle group, it was seen that the highest number of studies (22) focused on isometric unilateral knee extension exercises in which the target muscle is the quadriceps femoris (QF).

Training regimes (number of repetitions, number of sets, frequency of training sessions, rest in between sets and individual contractions, length of the individual contractions, total duration of the study), profile of the subjects (gender, age, weight, height) and changes in the MVC of QF were extracted. Data on the changes in neural properties (e.g. level of activation) and cross-sectional area and/or volume of the muscle were also extracted depending on their availability. A sensitivity analysis was performed on the extracted data to investigate which parameters influence the improvement in MVC and to what extent.

The results of the sensitivity analysis provided the parameters needed for formulating the adaptation equation that describes the change in strength throughout the training period. The adaptation equation is structured as an ordinary differential equation (ODE) with respect to the exercise input. The exercise input depicts the (cumulative) number of contractions for a given exercise regime (i.e. exercise input = repetitions/set x number of sets/training session x training sessions/week x total duration of the exercise in weeks).

A one-dimensional active muscle model that generates force upon the summation of individual motor unit firings was used to compute the MVC. In the model, the motor units are distributed between type I and type II. The force is generated by convoluting the twitch response of individual motor units with their respective firing times. The firing times of individual motor units are assumed to be statistically independent. The firing rate of individual motor units, the number of recruited motor units and their synchronization rate were altered in various combinations to match the improvement in MVC that is computed from the adaptation equation for a given exercise input.

Keywords: isometric exercise; skeletal muscle mechanics; systematic review; adaptation of skeletal muscles

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Fig. 1: Block diagram of the neuromuscular model

Object-oriented programming of optimized analytic neuromuscular model

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Abstract Each movement even the simplest is the result of complex interactions between several systems. The muscles responsible for the joint movement respond to a neural command controlled by the Central Nervous System. Then, muscles will generate several physical and chemical responses to this neural activation, i. e., calcium release, electrical activity and force generation. These muscle responses cannot be measured in experimental conditions without using an invasive protocol. Moreover, the interactions contributing to the muscle contraction cannot be experimentally determined. For this purpose, simulations can provide some new insights about the muscle contraction and a preliminary step before starting an experimental study. In this paper, we present the software structure of a neuro-electrical model (Carriou2016) describing the contraction of a muscle. We will point out the well suited object-oriented programming used to implement this model. Object-oriented programming is a programming concept based on macro structure containing data describing the object. Those objects can interact together through methods. Considering the complexity of the neuromuscular System of Systems (SoS) the first step before implementing the model is to clearly described the different systems and the interactions between them (see Fig. 1). Implementation of the model is made in Python programming language which is an interpreted language. To clarify each object and method developed in the model, a documentation is written within the model to describe how to use these features. Moreover, the Application Programming Interface (API) has been specified to simplify the use of the model through human readable definition of the model's input/outputs. One of the significant advantage of the object-oriented programming is the modularity of the computing code. In fact, this code modularity allows users to easily upgrade and extend the computing code to fit new functionalities (Al Harrach2017). Once these features considered, the management of the simulation computing time is the other challenge in muscle modeling. In the proposed model, reduction of the computing time is made at three levels. Firstly, optimization has been made on the mathematical equations describing the problem where all the calculus are considered in the Fourier domain to avoid the use of the convolution operator. Then, optimization procedures available with Python (list comprehension, code profiling, optimized libraries, etc.) were implemented in the model. Finally, thanks to all these features presented above, parallel computing has been easily integrated in the model, reducing significantly the computing time of the model. To conclude, considering the object-oriented programming for modelling the complex neuromuscular system seems to be well-suited for describing its composition and interactions (Carriou2016). Thanks to these integrated features in the model, upgrading the model to new methods or studies is feasible. Thus, a widespread use of this model in the scientific community can be considered.

Keywords: Neuromuscular system; System of systems; Object-oriented programming; Skeletal muscle model; Parallel computing; Analytic model;

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SESSION ABSTRACTS

Computational modelling of the dual action of parathyroid hormone in osteoporosis

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Abstract (500 words max). Osteoporosis is a disease characterized by long-term bone loss that occurs when bone resorption exceeds bone formation in the remodelling process. Progress has been made in the formulation of computational models of bone remodelling in order to take into account major cell-cell signalling pathways and regulatory mechanisms. Many hormones exhibit different release patterns, such as continuous or intermittent, which then modulate differential cell behaviours. In the bone literature, the most prominent example is the dual action of parathyroid hormone (PTH). It has been shown that a continuous administration of PTH leads to a catabolic effect on bone remodelling. On the other hand, daily subcutaneous injections of PTH constitute an effective anabolic treatment for osteoporosis. However, current computational models of bone remodelling are not able to distinguish between these two administration patterns. The purpose of our study was to develop a computational model of bone remodelling that takes into account the dual action of PTH. The model was built using human pharmacokinetics data, then calibrated and validated with data from postmenopausal osteoporosis (PMO).

The mechanism implemented in the model accounts for the anabolic effect of intermittent PTH on bone remodelling via the reduction of the apoptosis rate of active osteoblasts (OB). This mechanism involves the runt-related transcription factor 2 (Runx2) and the cAMP response element-binding protein (CREB). Runx2 is a mediator for the transcription of survival genes, such as B-cell lymphoma 2 (Bcl-2). The action of PTH on OB apoptosis is modeled with a system of three ODEs describing the intracellular signalling components (Runx2, CREB, and Bcl-2) as a function of PTH. Changes of Bcl-2 drive the reduction of OB apoptosis rate. This action is implemented in the model via a sigmoid E_{\max} function. The effect of PTH on bone remodelling is described by coupling the intracellular model of OB apoptosis together with a bone cell population model to compute changes over time of bone cell numbers and bone matrix fraction (f_{bm}). The latter quantities can be linked to bone turnover markers (BTM) and bone mineral density (BMD). To reproduce the change over time of PTH concentration in plasma under different dosing regimens, a pharmacokinetic (PK) model has been developed.

PMO is simulated with a rate of bone loss equal to 0.65%/year. The daily PTH subcutaneous injections are reproduced using a pharmacokinetic model. The computed apoptosis rate follows the intermittent behaviour of PTH, with an overall reduction in the daily average compared to baseline. The model shows a 3% trabecular f_{bm} increase from baseline after the simulation of 2 years of treatment. This value is consistent with the BMD increase measured at the femur neck and distal radius. Simulation of 40 μg PTH injections lead to a higher f_{bm} gain compared to the 20 mg dose. These results indicate that the model is capable of reproducing a dose-dependent gain in bone volume. By coupling the intracellular signalling of OB apoptosis and the bone remodelling process, our model can simulate the anabolic effect of intermittently administered PTH for PMO treatment.

Keywords: bone remodelling; bone mechanobiology; computational modelling; osteoporosis; pharmacokinetics; pharmacodynamics;

Assessment of the anisotropy of in vivo human skin: numerical simulations of multi-axial contact-free creep tests

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Abstract. Human skin is a living barrier between the outside influences and the inside of the body. It is a multi-layered complex structure composed of 4 main layers which are from the skin outer surface inward: the stratum corneum, the viable epidermis, the dermis and the hypodermis. The peculiar physiology of each layer is well adapted to its protective functions and influences the overall answer of the skin soft tissues to external loads. In particular, the dermis is a complex material made out of cells, an extra-cellular matrix, vessels and entities all bathed in a physiological fluid and structured by dense networks of collagen and elastin fibers. These networks give skin its mechanical structure not only at the dermis level but also in all other skin sub-layers. This results in layers of skin soft tissues considered as complex nonhomogeneous, anisotropic, nonlinear viscoelastic materials subjected to a prestress in vivo. Assessing quantitative and objective descriptions of these layers is a challenging issue in many surgical and medical domains and for every day quality of life of persons.

This paper proposes numerical simulations of multi-axial contact-free creep tests with the aim to investigate the anisotropy of the in vivo human skin materials and its consequences on the overall answer of the skin soft tissues.

The experimental tests are performed with the Waveskin[®] which is the contact-free indenter developed by the team of Prof. Hassan Zaouani at the LTDS (Laboratoire de Tribologie et Dynamique des Systèmes). This indenter is able to apply an air flow onto the external upper surface of the skin in vivo. During the tests, the deflection of the surface is recorded by a laser-line (length: 7 mm). It is important to notice that there exists no contact between the device and the skin before, during and after the tests. Therefore when the load is suppressed, the skin can freely come back to its natural state. Moreover this indenter is able to generate reproducible loads. Thus it is possible to generate cycles of identical loads. These cycles associated with different orientations of the laser-line (4 orientations) make it possible to perform tests equivalent to multi-axial contact-free creep tests. Following this procedure experimentations have been carried out on the volar forearm of two volunteers: a young woman and an old woman.

The 3D numerical simulations of these multi-axial contact-free creep tests are performed using the software SYSTUS[®]. They consider a skin specimen composed of 4 layers. Each layer simulates one of the main layers of the in vivo human skin. The key point of this paper is to consider an anisotropic behavior law to model the overall answer of the skin specimen. An inverse procedure is coupled with these simulations to characterize the mechanical parameters in different directions and investigate the influence of their different order of magnitude on the answer of the skin soft tissues. The numerical simulations provide also the stress fields in the volume of skin soft tissues. Starting from the study of these stress states, it will certainly be possible to establish a link between the physiology of the layers of skin soft tissues i.e. the fibers networks functions and the anisotropy observed at the outside skin surface and in its overall answer.

Keywords: human skin; numerical simulations; contact-free test; anisotropy; in vivo; multi-axial test

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Fig. 1 Human thermal plume (a), Cutaneous temperature map (b)

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Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) applied to Whole Body Cryotherapy (WBC)

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to develop a numerical model that can both predict the skin temperatures of the human body but also to accurately simulate the thermal plume that develops during a whole body cryotherapy (WBC) session. Whole Body Cryotherapy (WBC) can be considered as a therapeutic complement consisting to place the human body in a hermetic chamber, where the temperature varies from -60°C to -110°C for a short period of time (varying from 2 to 4 minutes). The objective is to stimulate the human body in order to activate natural defenses against the cold. This extreme temperature induces to the beneficiary a thermal shock thus activating biomechanical and biochemical survival reactions giving the ability to the human to perform a physiological shock. Extreme cold stimulates skin sensors, activating the Central Nervous System (CNS) response. This causes the release of endorphins, body's natural pain inhibitors and mood elevators, while the enhanced blood circulation activity decreases inflammation by clearing toxins and metabolic waste with a supply of oxygen and nutrient enriched blood to stimulate cellular regeneration. However, the self-protective mechanisms of the human body which are activated in case of prolonged exposure to extreme temperatures cannot go on forever. This is why it is essential to know precisely the thermal transfer occurring at the cutaneous surface of the patient during WBC session which is mainly due to the aerodynamic and thermal conditions within the cryotherapy cabin. In practice, accurate knowledge of the patient's skin temperature variation during a WBC session will help to limit the risks inherent in such a practice while maximizing the duration of the protocol. The experimental study is based on analysis of skin surface temperatures maps to obtain boundary conditions for the numerical problem. Indeed, the skin is considered as the main organ of study, place of thermal exchanges at the interface of the body (and its internal temperature) and the environment. The CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) model is thus a model of anisothermal fluid mechanics where free radiation and convection contribute to thermolysis losses. The modeling of the heat transfer between the energy production (metabolism) and losses leads to determine the thermal parameters which will constitute one of the thermal limit conditions of the problem to be modeled. The various steps of development of this numerical model are presented here and constitute the aim of the paper. First numerical results are also presented and are compared to experimental ones, particularly the skin temperature maps of the human body. Effects of the human thermal plume on the average velocity and temperature distribution within the cryotherapy cabin and around human are also investigated, considering fluctuation velocity, temperature and other unsteady characteristics.

Keywords: Cryotherapy; thermal plume; CFD simulation; skin temperature; convective-radiative model

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Fig. 1 a) *In-situ* custom-made device. b) Mice skin sample on which the microstructural acquisition are located. c) SHG acquisition acquired without loading.

The microscopic behavior of a Holzapfel-like model is supported only for low strain: application to mice skin

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Skin is a multi-layered composite structure, in which the most important is the dermis for the mechanical properties. The dermis is a “collagen-rich” tissue where the collagen network bathes in an extra-fibrillar matrix (proteoglycans, elastin, etc.), that induces a mechanical behavior involving structures at different scales. In this present study, a bi-axial tensile test coupled independently to a macroscopic measurement and a microscopic measurement was developed. The mechanical parameters of Holzapfel’s behavior were identified from a DIC (Digital Image Correlation) displacement field measurement, and the associated affine transformation was tested from microstructural SHG (Second Harmonic Generation) measurements.

First, a biaxial test (Fig.1a) was adapted from Bancelin et al. [1]. An alternated 10% loading was imposed successively on each arm, while measuring the displacement field and the force in each arm. Then, a FEMU (Finite Element Model Updating) approach was developed in order to minimize the quadratic discrepancy between experimental measurements (force and displacement field) and numerical data. Finally, the 5 parameters which govern the of Holzapfel’s behavior were identified on 6 mice: C_{10} describes the non-collagenous isotropic ground material behavior, k_1 and k_2 the contributions from collagen fibers, and κ the level of fiber dispersion along the mean fiber direction α ($0 \leq \kappa \leq \frac{1}{3}$).

Identification results showed a large variability on the angle α (from -7° to 80°). In addition, the distribution parameter (κ) presented always a value close to 0 that highlights a strong fiber orientation ($3.9 \pm 0.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$). The non-collagenous matrix (C_{10}) was always in the same range (104 ± 59 kPa) but seemed to be anti-correlated with the contributions from collagen fibers k_1 (55 ± 30 kPa) and k_2 ($25 \pm 3 \cdot 10^{-4}$). These results illustrated the interindividual and positioning variabilities.

Second, we observed the microstructure in 3 areas (center and 2 arms) across the loading (Fig.1b) with SHG microscopy (Second Generation Harmonic). It allowed us a local monitoring of the stretch thanks to the hair follicles and a local measurement of the collagen network distribution (Fig.1c). As presented in [1], the orientation index (OI) was computed to extract quantitative information from the fiber distributions. In practice, this index informs us on the fiber alignment along the direction of traction. Holzapfel’s behavior implying an affine transformation [2], the evolution collagen network is easily calculated knowing the kinematic of the transformation and the initial distribution.

The results presented a good agreement between the affine model and the experiment. This validates the model for low local stretches whatever the observed area. Nevertheless, for stretches above 1.2, the affine assumption was not relevant.

Despite many studies of the GOH-like model, this study highlighted the limits of the affine transformation assumption. Therefore, it would be interesting to develop models in which the fibers interact at the microscopic scale to give microstructural information in simulations.

Keywords: Identification, Affine transformation, Microstructure, Holzapfel's behavior, Mice skin

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Fig. 1 Attachment regions of scapula and humerus bones. A: Posterior view of right scapula with the final selection of VIDs of: I-S= Infraspinatus (Red), Suprasp= Supraspinatus (Light Blue), T-Maj = Teres major (yellow), T-Min= teres minor (Dark blue). B: anterior view of right humerus with the final selection of VIDs of Subscap = subscapularis (Pink), Suprasp=Supraspinatus (Blue) and T-Maj=Teres major (yellow).

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Subject-specific Shoulder Muscle Attachment Region Prediction Using Statistical Shape Models: A Validity Study

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Abstract: Subject-specific musculoskeletal models (MSKMs) can predict accurate joint and muscle biomechanics. However, assumptions made about the input model parameters make them generic and limit their clinical utility. Shoulder MSKM faces a huge challenge of subject specificity, in particular, muscle origin/insertion sites are always almost approximated. This considerably affects the muscle force and moment arm predictions and thus cannot be effectively used for pre-surgical or for rehabilitation assessments. In this study, we present a statistical shape model (SSM) based pipeline of using the SSM's ability to incorporate statistical variability for predicting subject-specific muscle regions in shoulder muscles. We also report the concurrent validity of the muscle origin/insertion region prediction on a randomly selected population of shoulder bones (scapula and humerus).

A database of dry bone samples (27 scapulae and 28 humeri) was used for building the bone SSMs using previously published IMCP-GMM pipeline [1]. The bone SSMs were then augmented with five muscle attachment (origin/insertion) regions (Subscapularis, Supraspinatus, Infraspinatus (I-S), Teres Major (T-Maj) and Teres Minor) on both the bones. For each bone surface mesh of the database in correspondence, origin/insertion regions were identified and masked by two experts using Meshlab (<http://meshlab.sourceforge.net/>). Inter-rater reliability for two randomly selected muscles was quantified by comparing the area of each muscle region obtained by each expert on each bone and also by quantifying dice similarity coefficient for each muscle region. The regions were represented by subset of vertices on the bone meshes and were tracked using vertex identifiers (VIDs). Using the correspondence within the database, a subset of vertices representative of each muscle was extracted and identified on mean shape of the bone SSM, by exploring the frequency of appearance of each point (VID) in the same muscle for the whole database (Fig. 1). To avoid the overlapping between muscle attachment sites, a frequency of 60% was selected to ensure the exclusivity of each VID for a single muscle region. Subject-specific muscle attachment regions were predicted using external set of bones not used in building the SSMs. An open source toolbox SCALISMO [2] was used to create and perform functions related to augmented SSMs.

Excellent intra-class correlation coefficient (ICC) for inter-rater reliability was reported for the two muscle origin/insertion regions on scapula (I-S (ICC = 0.927) and T-Maj (ICC = 0.942)), as well as, on the humerus (I-S (ICC = 0.981) and T-Maj (ICC = 0.962)). Dice coefficient ranged from 0.821 to 0.987 indicating a high region similarity between experts. Validity of region prediction was visually confirmed by the expert in ten external scapulae and eight external humeri. Excellent concurrent validity of muscle region prediction was observed based on the mean and root mean square distance measures and also based on similarity coefficient. We assumed that bone shapes can predict muscle origin/insertions regions and the excellent concurrent validity results confirm this for five major shoulder muscles on both the bones. The SSM based MSKM pipelines seems to be a good approach however, further validations are warranted on all the muscles of the shoulder complex.

Keywords: shoulder biomechanics, muscle insertion prediction, SCALISMO, point correspondence

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Integrated vs. multi-level/multi-scale spatial temporal modeling of ammonia detoxification after drug-induced liver damage: using modeling to guide towards a new therapy approach

Keywords: integrated modeling; compartment modeling; multiscale modeling; spatial-temporal modeling; agent-based modeling; liver damage; detoxification; model-guided experimentation; therapy

Hyperammonemia is a severe complication after drug induced liver damage, for example resulting from overdosing acetaminophen (paracetamol), and can lead to encephalopathy and death of the patient. A set of chemical reactions identified by Häussinger (1983) and Gebhardt (1983) has become the biological consensus model for ammonia detoxification in healthy liver.

We will show how the iterative application of a pipeline consisting of confocal scanning microscopy, image analysis and modeling can be used to design predictive models of tissue regeneration and metabolism suited to guide modeling driven experimental strategies (Drasdo et. al., 2014). As an example we will present an integrated model, integrating a compartment model of ammonia detoxification and a spatial-temporal micro-architectural agent-based model of liver regeneration after drug induced liver damage, that was able to identify lack of a critical ammonia sink mechanism in the consensus reaction scheme (Schliess et. al., 2014). The finding has led to identification of a so far unrecognized ammonia sink mechanism that could be experimentally demonstrated to represent a potential therapy approach in hyperammonemia (Ghallab et. al, 2016). In a further step we redo the analysis in a full spatial temporal micro-architecture model of the smallest virtual functional micro-anatomical unit (called lobule) obtained from image analysis (Hammad et. al., 2014; Friebel et. al., 2015) whereby the detoxification reactions are executed in each individual hepatocyte. Comparison between integrated and full multiscale modeling identifies transport / reaction conditions under which critical differences between both approaches are to be expected.

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Intra-operative quantitative estimation of liver function with indocyanine green fluorescence measurements

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Abstract (500 words max).

Liver transplantation and liver partial ablation are surgeries performed to treat liver diseases (cirrhosis, liver cancer). These surgery complications are related to a poor liver function, thus the evaluation intra-operatively of the hepatic function is an important clinical question. The liver function can be evaluated with blood sample analysis (for example by quantifying the level of bilirubin). Since the indocyanine green is a fluorescent dye exclusively removed from the blood by the liver cell, another method for liver function estimation is the indocyanine green clearance (plasma disappearance rate). However, these methods require time and therefore are not intra-operatively available. Besides, they only provide a combined information about possible perfusion/liver functions dysfunction.

In this work, we propose a framework to evaluate the liver function intra-operatively, based on a pharmacokinetics model and its parameters identification, analyzing the indocyanine green fluorescence dynamics in the liver tissue.

In [1], the measurements of liver tissue concentration of indocyanine green are fitted with a sum of two exponential functions (with two parameters) for six groups of rabbit with different treatments (colchicine, vessel occlusion...). In this work, the indocyanine green fluorescence is measured in the liver blood vessels, the liver tissue and the common bile duct, before or after liver partial ablation on pigs. The measurements enable to develop a mathematical model representing the indocyanine green processing from its removal from blood by the hepatocytes to its secretion into bile. The model focuses on a precise description of the dye processing by the liver, including the three different types of liver tissue (the sinusoids, the hepatocytes and the bile canaliculi). This model enables to precisely study the exchanges between the different liver tissues. This is a novelty compared with the previous model proposed in literature.

First, the model's outputs sensitivity to parameter is analyzed, and then the parameter estimation is performed with a population approach using Monolix software [2]. The parameters are estimated with the fluorescence measurements from pig surgeries. The link between the model's parameters and liver function is investigated. Then, the model is adapted to clinical constraints. Since more data is available during pig surgeries, the procedure is first tried out with a subset of measurements from pig surgery that would be available in the clinics. Then, a feasibility study is performed on a few measurements from patients after liver transplantation. The first results suggest that the liver surgeries impact the exchange between blood and liver cells. This new framework may provide a new estimation of the liver function(s) intra-operatively.

Keywords: Pharmacokinetics models; parameter estimation; indocyanine green; liver function estimation

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On a Tri-Scale Multiphase Model for the Description of Perfusion coupled to Growth Effects in Human Liver

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The human liver regulates metabolism in a complex time depending and non-linear coupled function-perfusion-mechanism. The viability of the organ is affected by a failure in the liver structure. A common chronic disease is the excessive accumulation of fat in the tissue, known as a fatty liver. The growing fat proportion has a high impact on the perfusion of blood through the liver. A central task of the human liver is the clearance of toxic metabolites which can be found in several medications. The clearance capacity of the human liver depends on an unimpaired perfusion of the blood through the vascular system and micro circulation. Since fatty liver growth influences the perfusion we claim that a fatty liver impacts the recommended dose of daily medicines.

The anatomy of the organ is characterized by a complex vascular system which changes on the different size scales from a vascular branching tree to microvessels, called sinusoids in liver lobules. To capture the interplay between fat deposition arising in the microstructure and the perfusion on the organscale it is important to couple the processes on each scale. For this we present a computational model for the human liver which is composed of three coupled submodels for the organ-, lobule- and cellscale. With the whole organ model we present the effect of growing fat vacuoles in the liver cells, which are inhomogenously distributed on organ-scale, up to the total hepatic hemodynamics.

On the organscale we use a Bernoulli approach (laminar steady state) calculating the perfusion in the branching system of the vascular tree. The vascular system starts with a single branch and subdivides into smaller vessels ending up in the portal triad - the interface of the organscale to the lobulescale. With a computation of the vascular perfusion we provide information of the blood velocity and pressure as boundary condition. The lobulescale uses a homogenized mixture model for the simulation of important functionalities in the liver lobules as presented in [2] including microperfusion, growth aspects and clearance capacity. The approach uses the extended theory of porous media (eTPM) [1] to consider the biological tissue as a multi-phase structure including the liver tissue, the fat vacuoles and the blood. On the microscale we focus on metabolic processes which take place in the liver cells.

Keywords: Tri-Scale Multiphase Model; eTPM; hepatic hemodynamics; growth; clearance

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Modeling of Field Potential in Microelectrode Arrays and Applications in Safety Pharmacology.

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Abstract

The study of the electrophysiological impact of drugs, e.g. in the CiPA initiative [1], are mainly addressed by three approaches: *in vitro* patch clamp assays; *in silico* Action Potential (AP) assays; *in vitro* assays on human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSC-CMs). The present work investigates a 4th direction: *in silico* assays on hiPSC-CMs.

The use of microelectrode arrays (MEAs) and hiPSC-CMs allows high-throughput screening of new drugs directly on human-derived cells. But the field potential (FP) signals acquired by MEAs are difficult to analyze. We believe that an *in silico* approach can improve the practical use of FP signals. The presentation will include a demonstration of a web application of our FP analysis tool.

Method: We developed a new strategy based on a mathematical model of MEA and an inverse problem. The model consists of the bidomain partial differential equations, coupled to a system of equations representing the ionic channels. The model provides both AP and FP, and can account for cell heterogeneities and imperfect contact with electrodes. Various devices (96-well and 6-well MEAs) and ionic models (Paci *et al.* for hiPSC-CM, or classical ionic models like O'Hara-Rudy or MV) were tested. An inverse problem algorithm was used to identify parameters of the ionic models from quantities measured on the FP.

Results: By extracting three biomarkers from real FP data for various drugs, the proposed identification algorithm provided concentration-response curves for potassium, sodium and calcium channels. IC50 determined by simulation were in good agreement with literature values (2.8uM for Ivabradine, 114uM for Moxifloxacin).

Conclusion: The forward simulations provide signals qualitatively close to those experimentally observed. They give new insights into some aspects of the FP difficult to address in real experiments, like the variability of the measurements, even in absence of variability of the cells. The inverse problem allows us to estimate the conductance of some channels and to obtain dose-response curves directly from FP measurements.

Keywords: cardiac electrophysiology; safety pharmacology; hiPSC-CM; MEA;

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Study of the effect of partial hepatectomy on liver function through modeling of ammonia detoxification.

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Abstract

Along with the kidney, liver is one of the main detoxifying organs, with a remarkable regenerative capacity. To treat some diseases, as liver cancer or cirrhosis, the damaged part of the liver can be surgically removed. Within a few days, liver will grow back to its original weight. After surgery the liver mass is reduced which can impair its ability to detoxify the blood from ammonia. Yet ammonia concentrations in the blood above a certain threshold for too long can cause brain damage and in extreme cases death.

This study aims at studying the influence of partial hepatectomy on liver function through the study of ammonia detoxification. We have developed a multi-scale model of ammonia detoxification after partial hepatectomy, taking into account its metabolism in the cells as well as the spatial inhomogeneities within the liver. From experimental confocal images of liver tissue before and after partial hepatectomy analyzed in TiQuant [1], statistically representative functional and anatomical units of the liver, liver lobules, at different time points have been generated. Blood flow is modeled as a resistive network, taking into account the effect of red blood cells. Using a representative liver lobule permits a precise definition of boundary conditions. This results in a large algebraic system of equations. Transport of ammonia in the blood, modeled by a 1D transport PDE, is coupled with its metabolism in the cells modeled by non-linear first order ODEs, through a passive uptake of ammonia. The metabolism model inside the hepatocytes is calibrated on healthy and drug-induced-damaged liver [2].

Ammonia levels at the liver outlet are predicted, from known input levels. This study has been done for mice and an extension to pig will be investigated.

This multi-scale model can be easily extended to any drug, marker or metabolite, as long as its metabolic pathways are known.

Keywords: tissue functional unit; ammonia metabolism simulation; sensitivity analysis; compound transport and metabolism; liver; microcirculation

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Simulation of fractional flow reserve and plaque development in the coronary arteries

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Abstract. The objective of this work was to compare computer simulation of plaque development and Fractional Flow Reserve (FFR) with standard angiography patient data. We simulated of the plaque formation with mass transport of LDL through the wall which is coupled with the Navier-Stokes equations, the Darcy equation for model blood filtration and Kedem-Katchalsky equations. Additional three reaction-diffusion equations for the inflammatory process and lesion growth model in the intima were used. Outlet boundary conditions were prescribed as inverse resistance from the corresponding diameter. Hemodynamic FFR threshold was observed for 0.80 and 0.75. We found a good correlation between real and computed FFR results on ten patients ($p < 0.005$). Computer simulation may predict plaque development and non-invasive anatomic and functional assessment of coronary stenosis for each specific patient which may be a clear benefit for patient study.

Keywords: plaque development; FFR simulation; coronary arteries

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Fluid-structure-interaction model of Transcatheter Aortic Valve Implantation configuration: comparison with an in-vitro study

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Abstract: Transcatheter aortic valve implantation (TAVI) is the treatment of preference for patients who are too weak or ill to undergo major surgery. Though the clinical benefit of the treatment has been demonstrated, some post procedural complications have emerged. In particular, the occurrence of silent ischemic lesions and dementia is considerably higher than with surgical valve replacements (Kahlert *et al.*, 2010).

The source of these pathologies is still unclear, but a potential cause has been recently identified as haemodynamic perturbations downstream the valve (Ducci *et al.*, 2013). In fact, contrary to surgical valve replacements, TAVI produces a valve-in-valve configuration which alters the flow in the aortic root, and may establish haemostatic conditions typically associated with thrombus formation.

The aim of this study is to expand these findings through a numerical model, allowing to analyse to identify the thromboembolic risk in the various regions of the fluid domain, for different configurations.

A fluid-structure-interaction (FSI) approach was chosen, in order to model the interaction of highly deformable structures with pulsatile fluid flows. The analyses were performed using the explicit finite element software LS-DYNA (LSTC, Livermore, CA, USA).

The models include the aortic root and the prosthetic valve, in an Eulerian fluid domain. Both the structure and fluid were meshed using ICM 17.0 (ANSYS, Inc., Canonsburg, PA, USA) and then exported to LS-DYNA. An arbitrary Lagrangian–Eulerian (ALE) algorithm was used to implement the coupling between the structural and fluid elements.

The numerical results were validated versus the flow patterns measured *in vitro* with particle image velocimetry (PIV). The study confirms that the TAVI approach has a major impact on the flow pattern, leading to the formation of zones characterised by slow flow velocities which may promote pathological conditions. Once refined, the computational model could be used to predict the haemodynamics in diseased and virtually treated conditions, providing a more appropriate tool for therapeutic planning and for the design of new improved devices.

Keywords: Fluid-structure-interaction (FSI), Transcatheter aortic valve implantation (TAVI); Arbitrary-Lagrangian-Eulerian technique (ALE); Valsalva sinus; blood stagnation

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Patient-specific numerical FSI model for bile flow simulation based on inter-disciplinary studies

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Abstract. The given study presents the results of patient-specific modelling using FSI algorithm to evaluate bile velocity and pressure distributions as well as the wall shear stress and von Mises stress distributions in the extra-hepatic biliary tree. Bile rheology in the healthy and pathological states was determined. It was confirmed that normal bile can be modeled as Newtonian fluid and lithogenic bile can be modeled as non-Newtonian fluid (Carreau fluid). The comparison between healthy bile (considered as Newtonian fluid) and lithogenic bile (considered as non-Newtonian fluid (Carreau fluid)) was made. Moreover, some cases dealing with gallstone presence influence on bile flow dynamics was also examined. Bile ducts were modeled as hyperelastic material (Mooney-Rivlin hyperelastic model). The constitutive parameters were obtained from performed inflation tests. The patient-specific biliary tree model was created using MRI and imported in FEM Commercial Package. The velocity and pressure distributions during the gallbladder emptying were presented. Velocities were found to have lower magnitude in the case of lithogenic bile, but the pressures are higher in this case. Stress state of bile ducts was also evaluated. It was shown that von Mises stress distribution is located in the cystic duct and hepatic ducts mostly; whereas, the shear stress distribution is mostly prevailing in the common hepatic duct. It is believed that duct wall shear stress can be considered as indicator of gallstones formation and von Mises stress is related to biliary pain. The developed model can be applied in the medical practice to evaluate the circumstances of surgical interventions.

Keywords: bile, biliary tree, patient-specific modeling, Mooney-Rivlin model, Carreau fluid, FSI

Fig. 1 Velocity distribution during the gallbladder emptying for non-Newtonian (lithogenic) bile

Fig. 2 Pressure distribution during the gallbladder emptying for non-Newtonian (lithogenic) bile

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Blood flow numerical simulation in a realistic liver model : effect of blood pressure on the liver rigidity

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Abstract

In the context of soft tissue mechanobiology, numerical models have the advantages of providing information that will help physicians, biologists, mechanics, surgeon and more generally all people in need of predictive tools to bridge the physiological biology and solid physics. More specifically, for mini-invasive surgery of liver tumor resection, real time augmented reality [1] provide the surgeon with a lot of information in 3D that can help him in making the right surgical decisions. The numerical models require to be computed quickly to provide pre and per-operation 3D real time data [2], while providing a high level of precision. Although parametric approaches like Proper Generalized Decomposition (PGD) Method allow a real-time response [3], they require the numerical model to integrate simplified mechanical behaviors [4]. In the context of the 3D-SURG project, we use homogenization techniques to develop a simplified mechanical model of the liver including its vascularisations and feed the Proper Generalized Decomposition.

First, geometries of the liver and its vascularisations are obtained from patients imaging data (MRI or CT scan). The mechanical properties of each material are extracted from experimental tests from non-invasive techniques. Based on these data, numerical mechanical tests, such as indentation, are applied on the different patient cases, integrating the vascularisation vessels walls and blood pressure, to identify the corresponding macroscopic mechanical behavior. Once the mechanical impact of those microstructures identified, a complete homogenized numerical model is developed providing precise deformations and displacements. Finally, a multi-layer homogenization is made to extract the numerical macroscopic homogenized material properties.

In the proposed study we will focus on the blood flow behavior in the liver vascularisations that will be later integrated in the homogenized numerical model. The overall geometry is decomposed in three parts : the incoming flow through the vena porta, the liver (considered as an equivalent porous media) and the outgoing flow through the vena cava. The three domains are coupled in the same simulation and solved for unsteady realistic flow rates.

Keywords : liver ; vascularisation ; CFD simulation

Fig. 1 : Topology of the realistic model; wall pressure and streamlines in the vena porta.

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Model-based analysis and design of gene regulatory networks: A computational framework

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Abstract. Computational and mathematical models have significantly contributed to the rapid progress in the study of gene regulatory networks (GRN), but researchers still lack a reliable model-based framework for computer-aided analysis and design. Such tool should both reveal the relation between network structure and dynamics and find parameter values and/or constraints that enable the simulated dynamics to reproduce specific behaviors. We address these issues and propose a computational framework that facilitates network analysis or design. It follows a modeling cycle that alternates phases of hypothesis testing with parameter space refinement to ultimately propose a model network that exhibits specified behaviors with the highest probability. Hypothesis testing is grounded on an automated simulator of the qualitative dynamics of the hypothesized models (Ironi, Tran (2016)). Such a tool, called GRENS, operates in presence of incomplete knowledge of parameter values and assumes that regulation is modeled by steep sigmoid functions and incompletely known parameter values by order relations only. Given as input an ODE model of a GRN, initial conditions and parameter space, it provides *all* sound symbolic/qualitative predictions of the nonlinear and temporal multiscale dynamics in *a single run*. Each simulated trajectory is characterized by delimited ranges of parameter values and by its qualitative dynamical property, e.g., stable or cyclic solution or damped oscillations. Parameter space refinement optimizes parameter stochastic values initialized by probability distributions with large variances (Ironi, Lanzarone (2014)). It is grounded on a method that computes the probability of occurrence of each predicted trajectory, labeled by a sequence of parameter inequalities, by associating probability density functions with network parameter values. Thus, we take into account the intrinsic stochasticity of regulation by assuming that network uncertainty is expressed by fluctuations in parameter values only. The integration of the qualitative and stochastic aspects provide powerful insights to the study of GRNs because: (i) the qualitative simulation allows us to predict all possible system behaviors, and (ii) the stochastic parameters to predict the likeliness of occurrence of a specific behavior. Taken all-together, the modeling cycle becomes a process of development, ranking, and eventually choice of a network as the best one for explanation and analysis or implementation by the synthetic biologists.

The power and ease of our framework is demonstrated by working out a benchmark synthetic network to get a synthetic oscillator.

Keywords: Gene regulatory networks; nonlinear and temporal multiscale ODE models; Qualitative dynamics; stochastic parameters; Systems and Synthetic Biology.

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migration. Altogether, data suggest that our coupled cell-ECM model can capture important features of single cell migration and cell-matrix interaction. By validation with and feedback to experiments, this model can therefore aid in unravelling the mechanisms behind cell-matrix interaction.

Keywords: smoothed particle hydrodynamics, deformable cell model, cell migration, viscoelastic extracellular matrix, degradation

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Fig. 1 Displacement field in the ECM around a deformable cell model that adheres to the ECM by contractile filopodia on opposing sides.